

**EVALUATION OF AWARENESS OF HEALTHCARE WORKERS TOWARDS
TELEHEALTH AS A COMPONENT OF HEALTH INFORMATICS A CASE
STUDY OF (AKTH) AMINU KANO TEACHING HOSPITAL, KANO-
KANO STATE- NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Telehealth involves medical information transfer from one side to another through electronic communication to improve patient health care. It's actively condition ranging from simplex to complex ones (Adebola, 2013). Telehealth may be as simple as two medical professionals discussing a case over the telephone or as advance or using videos, teleconferencing system.

This study aims to assess the evaluation of awareness of healthcare workers towards telehealth as a component of health informatics a case study of (AKTH) Aminu kano teaching hospital kano state.

Methods: A descriptive study design was employed, utilizing structured questionnaires distributed to 125 staffs of health records department in Aminu Kano teaching hospital Kano state (AKTH). The questionnaire assessed evaluation of awareness of healthcare workers towards telehealth as a component of health informatics case study of (AKTH) Aminu Kano teaching hospital Kano state. A Primary data analysis was employed in collecting facts and figures relating to the population in question i.e. AKTH Aminu Kano teaching hospital. This is to ensure that the exact information needed were obtain from respondents.

Results: The findings showed that Table 4. 2 show the age groups of the respondents in which 38 respondents representing 47% that are between the ages of 29-39 and it's the highest percentage table 4.7 shows that 30 respondents representing 37% of the respondents agreed that security measures is one of the challenges that hindered the use of telehealth and it's the highest percentage, Table 4.18 shows that 35 respondents representing 43% of the respondents that were strongly disagreed that higher revenue is the another uses of telehealth and it's representing the highest percentage.

Conclusion: In conclusion, findings suggest that staffs were aware of the impact of telehealth but the hospital lacks equipment for telehealth.

Keywords: Healthcare, Telehealth, Health informatics, component.

1 INTRODUCTION

Telehealth involves medical information transfer from one side to another through electronic communication to improve patient health care. It's actively condition ranging from simplex to complex ones (Adebola, 2013). Telehealth may be as simple as two medical professionals discussing a case over the telephone or as advance or using videos, teleconferencing system.

E-health on the other hand, is health care supported by electronic process and communication at the 2009 telemedicine conference held in Lagos. The Federal Ministry of Health disclosed its readiness to establish a National Coordinating Mechanism to coordinate e-health activities in the country in accordance with the World Health Organization (WHO) resolution passed in 2005. The Minister then promised that the ministry should establish a national e-health committee to work on developing a policy framework for under implementation in the nation's health sector. World Health Organization (WHO) resolution passed in 2005.

Objective of the Study

The general objective was to assess the evaluation of awareness of healthcare workers towards telehealth as a component of health informatics a case study of (AKTH) Aminu kano teaching hospital kano state.

The specific objectives are:

1. To find out the challenges that hindered the use of telehealth in Aminu Kano teaching hospital (AKTH)
2. To identify the areas in which telehealth is useful in health care delivery system in Aminu Kano teaching hospital (AKTH).
3. To identify the improvement that Telehealth brought in the health care delivery system in the Aminu Kano teaching hospital (AKTH).

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Design

A descriptive survey approach was used to evaluate 125 staffs of health records department in Aminu Kano teaching hospital Kano state (AKTH) regarding their awareness of healthcare workers towards telehealth as a component of health informatics.

Research Setting

Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital is a Federal Government Teaching Hospital located in Kano State, Nigeria. It was formerly known as Bayero University Teaching hospital. The current chief medical director is Abdurrahman Abba Sheshe. Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital serves three main functions: training of medical students and Resident doctors, provision of specialist medical services to the sick, and important research for the advancement of medical knowledge. The hospital is effective in training of

Bayero University medical students and postgraduate medical doctors (residency training). It recorded success over the years, including being the first government hospital to perform a successful kidney transplant in the year 2002, and the former Chief Medical Director Professor Abdulhamid Isa Dutse was instrumental in the transplant.

Target Population

The target population for this study includes 125 staffs of health information management department of Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital is a Federal Government Teaching Hospital located in Kano State, Nigeria.

Sampling Technique

A systematic random sampling was used to select participants to ensure that every individual in the population had an equal chance of being selected.

Instruments for Data Collection

A self-developed, structured questionnaire was employed to collect information from the selected participants.

Method of Data Collection

The questionnaires were distributed with clear instructions. Data were collected over three to four weeks. Each respondent's consent was also obtained by explaining the purpose of the research, and confidentiality was maintained.

Method of Data Analysis

The data was analyzed using the IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (IBM SPSS) Statistical software, version 29.

Ethical Consideration

Participants were fully briefed about the study purpose and the procedures for data collection in clear language that they could understand (English and Hausa languages respectively). All the data collected was anonymised to ensure that participants' identities were protected.

3 RESULTS

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of the socio-demographic characteristics of respondents.

Age	Frequency	Percentage
20-29	38	47%
30-39	30	38%
40-and above	12	15%
Total	80	100%

The table 1.1 shows the age groups of the respondents in which 38 respondents representing 47% that are between the ages of 29-39, while 30 respondents representing 38% of the respondents that are belong to the age's group of 38% and Only 12 respondents representing 15% of the respondents that are at the age's

group of 40- above years respectively.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of the challenges that hindered the use of telehealth in Aminu Kano teaching hospital AKTH Kano.

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agreed	30	37%
Agreed	20	25%
Strongly disagree	10	13%
Disagreed	15	19%
Undecided	5	6%
Total	80	100

The table in 2 shows that 30 respondents representing 37% of the respondents strongly agreed that security measures is one of the challenges that hindered the use of telehealth in Aminu Kano teaching hospital AKTH Kano, while 20 respondents representing 25% of the respondents were agreed, followed by the 15 respondents representing 19% were disagreed, and 10 respondents representing 13% of the respondents that were strongly disagreed and the remaining 5 responded representing 6% of the respondents respectively.

Table 3 Lack of awareness is one of the challenges that hindered the use of telehealth is security measures in Aminu Kano teaching hospital AKTH kano.

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agreed	35	43%
Agreed	20	25%
Strongly disagree	7	9%
Disagreed	8	10%
Undecided	10	13%

Total	80	100%
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The table in 3 shows that 35 respondents representing 43% were strongly agreed, followed by the 20 respondents representing 25% were agreed, while 7 respondents representing 9% were strongly disagreed and 8 respondents representing 10% were disagreed and the remaining 10 respondents representing 13 % of the respondents that were undecided that lack of awareness is one of challenges that hindered the use of telehealth in Aminu Kano teaching hospital.

Table 4 Difficult to access is one of the challenges that hindered the use of telehealth is security measures in Aminu Kano teaching hospital AKTH Kano.

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agreed	29	36%
Agreed	30	37%
Strongly disagree	11	14%
Disagreed	9	11%
Undecided	1	1%
Total	80	100%

The table in 4 show that 30 respondents representing 37% were agreed, while 29 respondents representing 36% of the respondents that were strongly agreed that difficulty in access is one of the challenges that hindered the use of telehealth in Aminu Kano teaching hospital.

4 DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

The findings reveals that table 1.1 shows the age groups of the respondents in which 38 respondents representing 47% that are between the ages of 29-39, while 30 respondents representing 38% of the respondents that are belong to the age’s group of 38% and Only 12 respondents representing 15% of the respondents that are at the age’s group of 40- above years respectively. The table in 1.2 shows that 30 respondents representing 37% of the respondents strongly agreed that security measures is one of the challenges that hindered the use of telehealth in Aminu Kano teaching hospital AKTH Kano, while 20

respondents representing 25% of the respondents were agreed, followed by the 15 respondents representing 19% were disagreed, and 10 respondents representing 13% of the respondents that were strongly disagreed and the remaining 5 responded representing 6% of the respondents respectively. The table in 1.3 shows that 35 respondents representing 43% were strongly agreed, followed by the 20 respondents representing 25% were agreed, while 7 respondents representing 9% were strongly disagreed and 8 respondents representing 10% were disagreed and the remaining 10 respondents representing 13 % of the respondents that were undecided that lack of awareness is one of challenges that hindered the use of telehealth in Aminu Kano teaching hospital. The table in 1.4 show that 30 respondents representing 37% were agreed, while 29 respondents representing 36% of the respondents that were strongly agreed that difficulty in access is one of the challenges that hindered the use of telehealth in Aminu Kano teaching hospital.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research conducted on the evaluation of awareness of health care workers towards the use of telehealth as a component of health informatics a case study of Aminu Kano teaching hospital Kano was there are not equipment for telehealth but the staffs were aware on the impact of it.

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